
Online Reading Comprehension: Expanding Students' Understanding on the Internet

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Abstract

This paper aims to analyze mainstream technology and Internet-based learning and attempts to explore the possibilities of incorporating digital text into the curriculum. Where this paper came to answer two important questions namely how can technology increase reading comprehension skills and make readers more efficient in their L2? What is the position of teachers and students of English as a foreign language about the Internet application in the classroom?. This paper found that the reader can connect with the ideas and incorporate them into previously gained information; also, improving reading comprehension skills primarily requires motivation, mental frameworks for holding ideas, concentration and good study techniques. Moreover, Realizing and understanding the text is much more complex and practical than vocabulary familiarity
Keywords: Online Reading, Comprehension, Expanding, Understanding.

Introduction

Reading comprehension skills represent a transition from students' passive L2 knowledge into the active and fluent one. What is generally accepted both by the students and the teachers, is that the Internet offers a great deal of information to the reader much faster than the traditional methods can do. Readers are now just a click away from entering many libraries and academic databases that they require for their improvement. EFL teachers use the Internet more and more frequently to facilitate classroom teaching and enhance the learning process for making students involved readers.

Problem statement

The Internet's domination in our everyday lives has led to the massive use of electronic reading systems for digital text in all fields of study. Due to that fact, the majority of language learners worldwide resort to finding reading materials that advance and support their learning. This essay aims primarily at analyzing the prevailing of technology and Internet-centered learning and tries to explore the possibilities of integrating the digital text into the curriculums.

Research questions

Two target questions addressed here are:

- i. How can technology increase reading comprehension skills and make the readers more proficient in their L2?
- ii. What is the attitude of EFL teachers and students towards implementing the Internet within a classroom?

Advantages and disadvantages of online learning

The Internet provides a wealth of resources and information that makes teaching exciting and interactive. It is also an ideal mechanism for encouraging students to take responsibility for their own learning. Incorporating the Internet into a classroom provides students with more opportunities to structure their own learning, to challenge themselves and compare their L2 knowledge to the rest of the online learners.

This powerful 24/7 resource network provides a vast amount of data otherwise not available in the students' geographical vicinity. Furthermore, it can enable readers to communicate with the world and implement various online surveys, for they are much faster and cheaper than the traditional survey methods.

Nevertheless, the Internet stumbles upon some disadvantages as well. One needs to be highly alert when using it, most of because of personal information thefts and virus threats. Internet is often attacked by cyber hacking, and it can store a lot of wrong and misleading information. Anyone can post anything, and the Internet still hasn't got a filter developed enough to shield itself from incorrect and offensive input. With its strengths, flaws, and its strategies in reading, the Internet has a significant effect on communicating, teaching, and learning. Thus, both teachers and learners should have the chance of Internet accessibility, experience and familiarity with its function in educational life.

Web pages and other digital media can enhance reading comprehension skills and vocabulary by providing students access to word pronunciation, word meaning, and contextual information. Many students shuffle between traditional and online reading or choose only one for different purposes. Sometimes they read for pleasure and/or for getting information. Their reading goal impacts the choice of their reading source. Throughout the reading comprehension process, readers become able to monitor the meaning they are constructing. Readers expect their reading material to make sense and to easily branch out to other similar topics. They use a repertoire of strategies, such as rethinking, re-reading or reading on to clarify ideas and remove misconceptions, if any. All of the aforementioned strategies develop students' multitasking and filtering skills, as well as obtaining data that truly meets their needs.

When discussing traditional and online reading resources, one can notice a few quite distinctive features between them. Traditional reading, the one that predominantly takes place at school, provides readers with texts that are more of a narrative nature, such as novels, stories, plays and poems. On the other hand, online reading material tends to be more informative and more objective. Also, reading tasks in a traditional setting usually involve the whole class or at least pair work, which is not the case with the online approach. Here, reading is highly individualized, i.e., requires a single participant only.

Moreover, the two reading approaches differ a lot when it comes to their originality and authorship. This is where the traditional reading materials seem to be more trustworthy. Online data is very easy to share, demanding little or no restrictions whatsoever. This represents one of the most drastic disadvantages of Internet information storage.

However, the information found in traditional reading materials generally includes texts and images only, while online information has got an abundance of hyperlinks, images, and audio-visual material that boosts reading experience and improves readers' concentration and memorizing.

One can hardly deny that the scene of education is changing rapidly and significantly. EFL teachers use the Internet more and more frequently to facilitate classroom teaching and enhance the learning process (Charupan; Soranastaporn; & Suwattananan, 2001). The majority of teachers admit and accept the fact that the Internet has become the most powerful and popular resource in L2 teaching and learning. They have integrated the Internet into the classroom for the simple reasons – it offers a wide spectrum of pedagogic possibilities, all the while serving as a mediating tool for creating technology-enhanced and student-centered learning environments (Fischer, 1999).

Dudency (2004); and Godwin-Jones (1998) have emphasized the importance of the Internet for English language teaching. Gilster (1997) stated that the Internet is “an interactive model of continuously updating information” that requires a rethinking of what it means to be a reader or even a literate person. Due to the invaluable role of the Internet technology in the classroom, it has become, as put by Chen (2008) “possible and feasible for language teachers to make effective use of instructional materials, especially in teaching language

and culture.” The Internet is limitless when it comes to ideas and topics it contains. Leu and Leu (1997) point out that electronic texts used in EFL classrooms enrich students’ interest and lead them to be good readers, truly involved in the meaning and the content appearing on their computer screens.

Furthermore, the Internet technology can be used to stimulate different tasks both in EFL classrooms and in readers’ private time, for example, online reading materials such as web newspaper and magazine sites and blogs, which prepare students to become life-long users of their L2 (Leloup & Ponterio, 2004).

The three basic elements of reading comprehension – the text, the reading activity, and the reader – occur within a large sociocultural context that influences how literate learners interpret and gather information. Also, the Internet keeps on expanding on a daily basis, and it influences the readers’ sociocultural milieu by providing collaborative opportunities for sharing and responding to information across continents, cultures, and languages.

Reading comprehension skills are best tested when readers are pushed to analyze and dissect their target language on their own. Online reading is a perfect field for such a challenge. Although vocabulary recognition, decoding, and fluency are cornerstones of effective reading, the ability to understand a text is only evident when readers can: “interpret and evaluate events, dialogue, ideas, and information; connect information to what they already know; adjust current knowledge to include new ideas or look at those ideas in a different way; determine and remember the most important points in the reading; read “between the lines” to understand underlying meanings” (<http://www.benchmarkeducation.com/best-practices-library/comprehension-strategies.html>).

Even though online reading is very individual and gives readers the amount of time they need to understand the text fully, the role of the teacher should not be neglected. Students are fast when making connections, asking questions, and visualizing the written data. However, they often find difficulty in identifying what is the main idea in the text, and in searching for clues and reliable evidence to make references and expand their knowledge. This is where the teacher steps in.

So, instead of interventions only, teachers’ approach should be a balance between traditional instructions (such as skimming and scanning the desired text) and a carefully planned effort to increase students’ self-efficiency and self-confidence. It appears to be most beneficial to give readers honest feedback about the things they are doing well, so they can relate their success to something within their control.

Many leading publishers and linguists nowadays turn to write books especially intended for online learning. One of the most influential computer companies in the world, *Apple*, has started using technology for teaching and learning purposes a while ago. Together with renowned linguists and experienced teachers, they have created *iBooks*, interactive documents that resemble regular books, but provide more external links and quicker access to reliable online databases.

The modern classroom provides a wide variety of programs and applications intended solely for learning languages. However, teachers should choose wisely and think about an app in terms of specific lessons and activities, and how it best supports what students are trying to achieve. The integration of the *iBook* app into the classroom will, therefore, be more successful if the teacher finds one *iBook* document that fits with the established lesson plan and rather than trying to implement one only because it is popular or entertaining for the students.

Depending on a school’s budget, technology can have an immense influence in classrooms. “The biggest challenge that it faces, however, is finding a way to integrate portable devices and apps into the existing curriculum and traditional practices. Current assessments and standards were formed without technology in mind, and it can be complicated to get them to work harmoniously” (<http://cehdvision2020.umn.edu/cehd-blog/aid-struggling-adolescent-readers/>).

It is a common belief among teachers that too much technology in the classroom does not actually help their students in the long run. A lot of them worry about situations where students will not have Internet access and whether they are able to readjust to traditional reading. With that in mind, it is quintessential to form a bridge between traditional print literacy with digital literacy in the foreseeable future.

Many online blogs have good exercises for practicing reading comprehensions, like Oxford and Cambridge blogs, and many others (<http://www.usingenglish.com/comprehension/5.html>). They offer different kinds of texts followed by related questions to be self-corrected. Thus the students can test themselves away from feeling embarrassed or/and anxious.

Some online reading programs offer improving reading comprehension skills through involved online episodes. These programs have research-based sequencing customized so to its assurance that the learners will receive the individualized instructions they need in order to increase test scores and advance their literacy in various classroom and everyday environments.

Conclusion

Improving online reading comprehension skills, the reader can connect with the ideas and incorporate them into previously gained information. For example, if a person likes science, then reading online scientific text comes easily. They have a framework in their mind, understand and collect vocabulary and can predict the writing style they will encounter.

Improving reading comprehension skills primarily requires motivation, mental frameworks for holding ideas, concentration and good study techniques. When a person reads a text, he engages in a complex array of cognitive processes. The reader is simultaneously using his/her awareness and understanding of separate words and the ability to comprehend or construct meaning from the text. This last component of the act of reading is reading comprehension. It cannot occur separately from the other two elements of the process. At the same time, it is the most difficult and most important of the three.

The two elements that strengthen the process of reading comprehension are vocabulary knowledge and text comprehension. In order to understand a text the reader must be able to comprehend the vocabulary used in the piece of writing. If the individual words don't make sense then the overall story will not either. However, text comprehension is much more complex and versatile than vocabulary knowledge. "Readers use many different text comprehension strategies to develop reading comprehension. These include monitoring for understanding, answering and generating questions, summarizing and being aware of and using a text's structure to aid comprehension" (<http://www.k12reader.com/what-is-reading-comprehension/>).

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